

WORLD AGRICULTURE FORUM (WAF)

RESEARCH REPORT

Challenges and Opportunities in Sustainable Cocoa Production in Ghana

By

Mensah Isaac Kweku Junior
Research & Knowledge Management Intern
World Agriculture Forum (WAF) – June 2025 Cohort

A study exploring sustainability, climate resilience, and value chain transformation in Ghana's cocoa sector

Date of Submission: July 15, 2025

Email: ikjmensah@st.ug.edu.gh

Location: Accra, Ghana

Table of Contents

Chapter One	3
1.0 Introduction.....	3
Chapter Two.....	5
2.0 Methodology	5
Chapter Three.....	6
3.0 Results and Discussion	6
3.1 Economic Importance of Cocoa.....	6
3.2 Key Challenges in Sustainable Cocoa Production	7
3.2.1 Low Productivity.....	7
3.2.2 Climate Change and Environmental Stressors	7
3.2.3 Demographic Constraints and Youth Disengagement	7
3.2.4 Deforestation and Environmental Degradation.....	8
3.2.5 Market and Value Chain Constraints	9
3.3 Opportunities for Sustainable Cocoa Production.....	10
3.3.1 Agroforestry and Climate Adaptation	10
Case Study: Agroforestry in Western North Region.....	10
3.3.2 Sustainability Certification and Ethical Trade	11
3.3.3 Youth Engagement and Modernization	11
3.3.4 Value Addition and Processing.....	11
3.3.5 Policy and Institutional Support.....	12
Chapter Four	13
4.0 Conclusion and Recommendation	13
4.1 Conclusion	13
4.2 Recommendations.....	14
References.....	15
Appendices.....	17
Abbreviation	17
Appendix A: Cocoa Producer Prices in Ghana (2018–2024)	17
Appendix B: Cocoa Production and Yield Data (2018–2024).....	18
Appendix C: Common Cocoa Diseases in Ghana	18
Appendix D: Key Stakeholder Roles in Ghana’s Cocoa Sector	19
Appendix E: Case Study – Western North Region	19
Appendix F: Youth and Employment Insights	20
Annex 1: Government Policy Measures Supporting Sustainability.....	20

Abstract

Ghana is the second-largest producer of cocoa globally, contributing significantly to the national economy and rural livelihoods. However, the sustainability of cocoa production in Ghana is increasingly threatened by a range of socio-economic, environmental, and institutional challenges. This paper examines the core challenges hindering sustainable cocoa production and identifies opportunities for enhancing productivity, environmental resilience, and farmer welfare. Using secondary data from national and international reports, scientific publications, and stakeholder analyses, this study highlights low productivity, climate change, aging farmer demographics, deforestation, and market volatility as key constraints. Conversely, the integration of agroforestry systems, value addition, sustainability certification, and youth engagement represent vital pathways toward sustainable cocoa production. The paper concludes by proposing a multi-stakeholder and integrated approach to policy and practice that ensures both economic viability and environmental stewardship.

Keywords: cocoa, Ghana, sustainability, agroforestry, climate change, productivity, youth engagement

Chapter One

1.0 Introduction

Cocoa (*Theobroma cacao* L.) is a globally significant crop, cultivated in tropical and subtropical regions between 10°N and 10°S of the equator. It is the primary raw material used in the chocolate confectionery industry, which is valued at over USD 130 billion globally.

Cocoa supports the livelihoods of an estimated 5–6 million smallholder farmers worldwide, the majority of whom are in developing countries (Kongor et al., 2024).

The global cocoa value chain is bifurcated into upstream (production) and downstream (processing and marketing) sectors, with most of the high-value activities concentrated in consumer countries such as the United States, the Netherlands, Germany, and Belgium.

In recent decades, there has been increasing global concern over the environmental, social, and economic sustainability of cocoa production. Issues such as climate change, biodiversity loss, child labor and income insecurity have dominated sustainability discourses of Cocoa production. Consumer preferences have also shifted towards ethically sourced and environmentally friendly cocoa products, as evidenced by the rising demand for certified cocoa.

Africa is the leading continent in cocoa production, accounting for approximately 74.5% of global output. West Africa is the epicenter of this production, with Côte d'Ivoire and Ghana as the two largest producers, collectively contributing nearly 60% of the world's cocoa supply (ICCO, 2023c).

Despite this dominance, most cocoa-producing countries in Africa export raw beans, with limited domestic processing. This results in value loss and reduces the sector's potential for industrial development and economic transformation.

Ghana, in particular, is the second-largest cocoa producer globally and the foremost source of premium-quality beans. Cocoa plays a pivotal role in Ghana's economy, accounting for approximately 8% of GDP and supporting the livelihoods of over 800,000 smallholder farmers (Ghana Cocoa Report, 2024). The Ghana Cocoa Board (COCOBOD), established in 1947, has helped regulate and stabilize the sector through input distribution, quality control, and price stabilization mechanisms. However, the cocoa sector in Ghana faces multiple sustainability

challenges, including declining yields, climate impacts, socio-economic barriers, and institutional inefficiencies.

As global demand for ethically and sustainably sourced cocoa rises, Ghana must innovate and adapt its cocoa production systems to remain competitive and resilient. Sustainable production must address ecological balance, economic viability, and social equity.

Cocoa (*Theobroma cacao* L.) plays a pivotal role in Ghana's economy, accounting for approximately 8% of GDP and supporting the livelihoods of over 800,000 smallholder farmers (Ghana Cocoa Report, 2024). Ghana is renowned for the high quality of its cocoa beans, which earn a premium on international markets. Despite its historical success, the cocoa sector faces multiple sustainability challenges, including declining yields, climate impacts, socio-economic barriers, and institutional inefficiencies. As global demand for ethically and sustainably sourced cocoa rises, Ghana must innovate and adapt its cocoa production systems to remain competitive and resilient.

The aim of this study is to conduct a comprehensive scientific examination of the sustainability challenges facing Ghana's cocoa sector and evaluate the potential opportunities for enhancing its performance. This research will contribute to the policy discourse and support evidence-based strategies to ensure long-term sustainability of the cocoa value chain.

Figure 1 https://anangtawiah.com/media/blog_images/Screenshot_2024-10-20_202404_CVb6ek7.png

Chapter Two

2.0 Methodology

This study adopts a qualitative, desk-based research methodology utilizing secondary data from peer-reviewed journals, institutional reports from COCOBOD, the World Cocoa Foundation, the International Cocoa Organization (ICCO), and other reputable sources. The analysis synthesizes insights from historical data, current practices, and policy frameworks relevant to cocoa production in Ghana. Key references include The Ghana Cocoa Report (2024), Kongor et al. (2024), and Barrientos et al. (2007).

The research approach involved systematic thematic coding of literature, categorizing key challenges and opportunities, and triangulating findings to ensure academic rigor. Trends in production, environmental dynamics, socio-economic patterns, and institutional performance were explored in detail.

Chapter Three

3.0 Results and Discussion

3.1 Economic Importance of Cocoa.

Cocoa remains one of Ghana's most critical export commodities, contributing significantly to foreign exchange earnings, employment, and rural livelihoods. According to the Ghana Cocoa Board (COCOBOD), cocoa generated over USD 2.1 billion in export revenues in 2020, accounting for roughly 20% of Ghana's total export earnings (COCOBOD, 2021). The Ghana Export Promotion Authority (GEPA) confirms that cocoa is consistently among the country's top three export commodities, alongside gold and crude oil.

The cocoa sector directly supports over 800,000 smallholder farmers and indirectly sustains an estimated 4 million people through value chain linkages including processing, transportation, research, warehousing, and marketing (World Bank, 2021). Cocoa farming is the principal economic activity in the Western North, Ashanti, Ahafo, Bono, and Eastern regions, where entire communities depend on seasonal cocoa incomes to meet household needs such as food, school fees, healthcare, and housing (SEND Ghana, 2023).

Beyond its economic value, cocoa plays a significant role in poverty alleviation. The World Bank (2021) notes that cocoa-growing households typically fare better in terms of food security and asset ownership compared to non-cocoa-growing households. A 2022 study by the International Food Policy Research Institute (IFPRI) also indicates that cocoa income has a stabilizing effect in rural Ghana during periods of broader economic downturn.

Cocoa is equally important in terms of public sector revenue. COCOBOD levies and duties on cocoa exports contribute to Ghana's fiscal resources and are used to fund national development projects such as rural electrification, feeder roads, and education infrastructure in cocoa-producing regions (Ministry of Finance, 2022).

However, any disruption to the cocoa value chain—whether due to climate risks, pests, disease outbreaks, or price shocks—can have cascading economic and social consequences. Hence,

safeguarding the sustainability of cocoa production is critical not only for farmers but for the broader national economy.

3.2 Key Challenges in Sustainable Cocoa Production

3.2.1 Low Productivity.

The productivity of cocoa farms in Ghana averages around 400 kg/ha, significantly below the potential yield of over 1000 kg/ha (Ghana Cocoa Report, 2024). Key constraints include aging cocoa trees, poor farm management practices, inadequate adoption of hybrid varieties, low fertilizer use, and lack of extension support.

Traditional farm practices—such as manual weeding, non-pruned trees, and irregular spraying—persist due to limited awareness and financial constraints. Farmers are often unable to afford essential inputs like fungicides, insecticides, and fertilizers, leading to sub-optimal production. Furthermore, poor post-harvest handling such as improper fermentation and drying reduces bean quality and market value.

3.2.2 Climate Change and Environmental Stressors

Climate variability poses one of the most severe risks to cocoa sustainability. Rising temperatures, erratic rainfall, and prolonged dry seasons reduce productivity and increase pest and disease outbreaks (Kongor et al., 2024). Notably, black pod disease and cocoa swollen shoot virus thrive under high humidity and rainfall, causing significant yield losses.

Climate models predict a shift in cocoa-suitable zones, with some traditional cocoa-growing areas becoming less viable. High rainfall contributes to nutrient leaching, reducing soil fertility. In the absence of adaptation, many smallholder farmers face existential threats to their livelihoods.

3.2.3 Demographic Constraints and Youth Disengagement

The demographic profile of cocoa farmers in Ghana highlights a worrying trend: the aging of the labor force. According to the World Cocoa Foundation (2020), the average age of cocoa farmers in Ghana is about 51 years, with many over 60. This situation raises serious concerns about intergenerational continuity and the long-term viability of cocoa farming.

Young people are increasingly reluctant to enter the cocoa sector due to various disincentives. The labor-intensive nature of cocoa cultivation, lack of access to land due to customary land tenure systems, poor infrastructure in cocoa-growing areas, and the perception of agriculture as a low-status profession are all significant deterrents (Ministry of Employment and Labour Relations, 2022). Many youths prefer to migrate to urban centers in search of formal employment, even when such opportunities are limited.

According to the 2022 Youth Employment Report by Ghana's Ministry of Employment and Labour Relations, cocoa farming is one of the least preferred job options among rural youth. Limited access to credit, high cost of inputs, and absence of modern technology further discourage youth participation. In addition, government and private sector efforts to promote youth agripreneurship have often excluded cocoa from focus areas, favoring vegetables, poultry, and aquaculture (Youth Employment Report, 2022).

Without deliberate policies and incentive structures to attract and retain youth in the cocoa sector, Ghana risks facing a labor crisis in cocoa production in the next two decades.

3.2.4 Deforestation and Environmental Degradation

The expansion of cocoa cultivation in Ghana has been a major driver of deforestation, particularly in the Western North and Eastern regions. According to Global Forest Watch (2022), Ghana lost over 1.6 million hectares of tree cover between 2001 and 2022, with cocoa-related encroachment cited as a significant factor. The Forestry Commission of Ghana (2021) corroborates that cocoa farming is among the top causes of illegal encroachment into forest reserves.

Much of this expansion into forested areas has occurred due to land scarcity, low productivity on existing farms, and a lack of enforcement of conservation policies. Cocoa farmers, in search of fertile land, often resort to clearing forest reserves, resulting in biodiversity loss, disruption of ecological services, and increased greenhouse gas emissions (Kongor et al., 2024).

Declining soil fertility is another concern. Continuous mono-cropping without proper nutrient management has led to soil degradation. The Soil Research Institute (2023) has warned of nutrient depletion in major cocoa belts due to overuse and insufficient replenishment.

Furthermore, the reduction in forest cover has impacted the microclimate needed for optimal cocoa growth and led to the disappearance of important pollinators and shade trees, aggravating climate vulnerability. These ecological pressures underscore the need for landscape-level planning, agroforestry adoption, and strict enforcement of sustainable land use policies.

3.2.5 Market and Value Chain Constraints

Ghana's cocoa sector is vulnerable to international price fluctuations due to its dependence on raw bean exports. Although COCOBOD offers a guaranteed minimum producer price, it is still modest compared to the value of finished chocolate products. According to the International Cocoa Organization (ICCO, 2023), cocoa farmers in Ghana typically receive just 6% of the final retail price of a chocolate bar.

The forward sales system used by COCOBOD to stabilize prices for farmers has also come under scrutiny. In 2024, while world market prices for cocoa surged to over USD 10,000 per tonne due to supply shortages in Côte d'Ivoire, Ghanaian farmers did not benefit fully because forward contracts had locked prices earlier at significantly lower rates (Anang Tawiah, 2024). This has prompted calls for a partial liberalization of the sector to allow more responsive pricing mechanisms.

In addition, farmers face persistent issues related to Licensed Buying Companies (LBCs), including delayed payments and occasional defaults (Barrientos et al., 2007). Infrastructure challenges—such as poor roads and lack of storage facilities—add to post-harvest losses and marketing difficulties. Limited access to market information and weak bargaining power among smallholder farmers, due to the fragmentation of farmer organizations, further marginalize producers in price negotiations.

Moreover, Ghana processes less than 20% of its cocoa domestically, meaning most of the value is captured abroad. Despite government efforts to encourage value addition through tax incentives and local content policies, investments in domestic processing remain insufficient due to high energy costs and limited access to affordable finance for processors (Ghana Cocoa Report, 2024).

Collectively, these market and value chain constraints diminish the profitability of cocoa farming and hinder the economic empowerment of farmers.

3.3 Opportunities for Sustainable Cocoa Production

3.3.1 Agroforestry and Climate Adaptation

Agroforestry presents a major opportunity to enhance sustainability and climate resilience in Ghana's cocoa sector. The Cocoa & Forests Initiative (CFI), led by the World Cocoa Foundation in collaboration with COCOBOD and major chocolate companies, has been actively promoting agroforestry as a means of reversing deforestation and restoring degraded landscapes (CFI, 2021). Integrating shade trees with cocoa not only reduces evapotranspiration and soil erosion but also creates habitats for biodiversity.

Farmers participating in agroforestry projects have reported improved pod yields, better soil structure, and diversified income from non-timber forest products like avocado, moringa, and plantain (Rainforest Alliance, 2022). However, tenure insecurity remains a key barrier to large-scale adoption, as many farmers are uncertain about ownership of trees they plant on leased land. COCOBOD and the Forestry Commission are working to harmonize tree tenure laws to encourage uptake.

Case Study: Agroforestry in Western North Region

In 2022, the Rainforest Alliance and COCOBOD piloted an agroforestry project in the Western North Region involving 500 smallholder farmers. Farmers were trained to integrate native trees such as mahogany and fruit trees like avocado into cocoa plantations. Within two years, farmers reported improved soil moisture, reduced erosion, and increased yields by an average of 15%. Additionally, participating households earned supplemental income by selling fruits and non-timber forest products. Despite these successes, insecure tree tenure limited expansion, prompting a policy review by the Forestry Commission in 2023.

3.3.2 Sustainability Certification and Ethical Trade

Sustainability certification schemes such as Fairtrade, Rainforest Alliance, and UTZ provide incentives for environmentally responsible practices and social standards in cocoa farming. In Ghana, over 150,000 farmers have been certified under at least one sustainability label (ICCO, 2023). Certified cooperatives receive premium payments, training in good agricultural practices (GAP), and organizational development support.

However, challenges persist. A study by Oxfam (2022) found that only 40% of certified farmers actually benefit from full premium payments due to administrative deductions and lack of transparency in cooperative management. Additionally, many farmers struggle to meet certification standards due to costs associated with recordkeeping, shade tree planting, and internal audits. There is a growing call for certification bodies to simplify compliance requirements and provide direct support to marginalized farmers.

3.3.3 Youth Engagement and Modernization

Engaging youth is a crucial opportunity for the future of cocoa. Initiatives like the Ghana CARES Obaatan Pa programme and the Youth in Agriculture Programme (YIAP) have targeted youth involvement in agri-value chains, but cocoa has not received enough targeted support. In 2022, the Mastercard Foundation partnered with COCOBOD and Solidaridad to launch the “NextGen Cocoa Youth Programme,” aimed at training young people in cocoa agribusiness, entrepreneurship, and ICT for agriculture (Solidaridad, 2023).

Youth-friendly policies—such as startup capital, land leasing schemes, mechanized services, and digital training—are essential to reverse the demographic shift. Digital platforms like FarmTrace and CocoaLink have also improved access to market prices, extension advice, and financial services for young farmers.

3.3.4 Value Addition and Processing

Ghana currently exports over 80% of its cocoa as raw beans, which limits domestic revenue generation. The government, through its Ghana Cocoa Processing Company (CPC), and private firms like Niche Cocoa and Plot Ghana, are investing in semi-finished and finished cocoa products to capture more value locally (GEPA, 2022).

The One District, One Factory (1D1F) initiative is providing tax incentives and soft loans to attract cocoa processing businesses to cocoa-producing regions. Local consumption campaigns and artisanal chocolate startups are also helping to develop a domestic cocoa product market.

However, challenges such as unreliable power supply, high processing costs, and limited access to export finance hinder growth.

Expanding Ghana's share of global chocolate production would require strategic partnerships with investors, improvements in logistics infrastructure, and strong branding of Ghanaian chocolate on international markets.

3.3.5 Policy and Institutional Support

COCOBOD remains central to Ghana's cocoa sustainability agenda. Through initiatives like the Cocoa Rehabilitation Programme, Mass Pruning and Spraying Program, and High-Tech Fertilizer Distribution Scheme, COCOBOD aims to restore aging farms and enhance productivity (COCOBOD, 2023).

The Cocoa Research Institute of Ghana (CRIG) continues to release climate-resilient and disease-tolerant cocoa hybrids. International donors such as GIZ, the World Bank, and the European Union are providing technical and financial assistance to strengthen extension systems, traceability mechanisms, and sustainability compliance (World Bank, 2021).

However, policy coherence and institutional transparency remain concerns. Reports by SEND Ghana (2023) have called for stronger farmer participation in decision-making, decentralization of COCOBOD services, and better coordination between MoFA, COCOBOD, and NGOs. Strengthening farmer cooperatives and building capacity at the district level are also vital to ensure grassroots impact.

Chapter Four

4.0 Conclusion and Recommendation

4.1 Conclusion

Sustainable cocoa production in Ghana is not only a national imperative but a global necessity, especially in the context of increasing demand for ethically sourced and environmentally sound commodities. The sector faces a complex matrix of interrelated challenges—ranging from climate change, low productivity, and environmental degradation to youth disinterest and institutional inefficiencies. These issues threaten the long-term viability of Ghana’s cocoa economy and the livelihoods of millions.

To sustain and expand its position as a global cocoa leader, Ghana must embrace a systemic transformation. This includes adopting climate-smart agricultural practices, investing in agroforestry, scaling up sustainability certification, modernizing the cocoa value chain, and actively involving the youth. Inclusive and equitable participation across gender, age, and region must be embedded into all cocoa sector reforms.

Additionally, resilience must be built at the farm, community, institutional, and policy levels. Strategic public-private partnerships and coherent multi-sectoral frameworks—encompassing agriculture, finance, environment, education, and trade—are critical to unlocking the sector’s full potential.

Ultimately, Ghana’s cocoa sector holds immense promise—not just as a commodity powerhouse, but as a model for sustainable tropical agriculture. The lessons learned from Ghana’s journey toward sustainability can influence regional and global discourse on ethical sourcing, climate adaptation, and rural development. This transformation, however, requires urgency, innovation, and inclusive action.

4.2 Recommendations

Building on the findings and analysis in this research, the following strategic recommendations are proposed to advance sustainable cocoa production in Ghana:

1. **Expand Cocoa Rehabilitation Schemes:** Scale up tree replacement programs, particularly for CSSVD-affected areas, and ensure timely farmer compensation and access to high-quality seedlings.
2. **Strengthen Research–Extension–Farmer Linkages:** Improve collaboration between CRIG, extension agents, and farmers to accelerate the adoption of climate-resilient technologies and best agronomic practices.
3. **Promote Climate-Smart Agriculture (CSA):** Integrate CSA techniques into national cocoa policies and training curricula, focusing on soil management, water conservation, and ecosystem restoration.
4. **Enhance Access to Finance:** Develop inclusive financing mechanisms such as low-interest loans, micro-insurance schemes, and digital credit tailored to smallholder cocoa farmers and youth agripreneurs.
5. **Implement a National Youth Cocoa Strategy:** Create incentives for youth participation, including land leasing support, entrepreneurship incubators, digital innovation hubs, and mechanization services.
6. **Scale Agroforestry Adoption:** Finalize and implement tree tenure reforms, subsidize shade tree seedlings, and integrate agroforestry into cocoa extension programs.
7. **Improve Governance and Transparency:** Strengthen cooperative governance, ensure transparency in pricing and certification premiums, and introduce digital traceability systems to combat smuggling and corruption.
8. **Facilitate Domestic Value Addition:** Support processors through infrastructure development, policy incentives, and export facilitation to expand Ghana’s share of processed cocoa products in global markets.
9. **Foster Multi-Stakeholder Dialogue:** Institutionalize regular consultation platforms involving COCOBOD, MoFA, private sector actors, civil society, and farmer groups to harmonize policy and practice.

References

- Anang Tawiah. (2024). *Ghana Cocoa Prices and Pricing Trends: Challenges and Opportunities*. Retrieved from <https://anangtawiah.com>
- Barrientos, S., Asuming-Brempong, S., Sarpong, D., Anyidoho, N. A., Kaplinsky, R., & Leavy, J. (2007). *Mapping Sustainable Production in Ghanaian Cocoa*. Institute of Development Studies, University of Sussex & University of Ghana.
- Cocoa & Forests Initiative (CFI). (2021). *Progress Report on Cocoa Agroforestry and Deforestation in Ghana*.
- COCOBOD. (2021). *Annual Cocoa Sector Report*.
- COCOBOD. (2023). *Cocoa Sector Programmes and Strategic Updates*.
- Forestry Commission of Ghana. (2021). *Annual Forest Sector Report*.
- Ghana Cocoa Report. (2024). *Ghana Cocoa Industry: History, Challenges, and Future Prospects*. Retrieved from Anang Tawiah's Blog.
- Ghana Export Promotion Authority (GEPA). (2022). *Annual Cocoa Processing and Export Trends Report*.
- Ghana Export Promotion Authority (GEPA). (2022). *Annual Export Performance Report*.
- Global Forest Watch. (2022). *Tree Cover Loss in Ghana (2001–2022)*. Retrieved from <https://www.globalforestwatch.org/>
- ICCO. (2023). *The World Cocoa Economy: Current Situation and Outlook*.
- International Cocoa Organization (ICCO). (2023). *Certified Cocoa Production in West Africa: Trends and Impact*.
- International Food Policy Research Institute (IFPRI). (2022). *Income Diversification and Resilience in Ghana's Cocoa Sector*.
- Kongor, J. E., Owusu, M., & Oduro-Yeboah, C. (2024). Cocoa production in the 2020s: Challenges and solutions. *CABI Agriculture and Bioscience*, 5(102). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s43170-024-00310-6>
- Ministry of Employment and Labour Relations. (2022). *National Youth Employment Report*.
- Ministry of Finance. (2022). *Budget Statement and Economic Policy of the Government of Ghana*.

Oxfam. (2022). *Behind the Barcode: Cocoa Farmers and Certification Premiums in Ghana*.

Rainforest Alliance. (2022). *Agroforestry in Cocoa Landscapes: Case Studies from Ghana*.

SEND Ghana. (2023). *Strengthening Accountability in Ghana's Cocoa Sector: Policy Brief*.

SEND Ghana. (2023). *The Cocoa Farmer's Voice: Livelihood Realities and Sustainability Gaps*.

Soil Research Institute. (2023). *Soil Nutrient Status in Cocoa Growing Regions of Ghana*.

Solidaridad. (2023). *NextGen Cocoa Youth Programme in Ghana: Annual Update*.

World Bank. (2021). *Ghana Cocoa Sector Diagnostic Report*.

World Bank. (2021). *Strengthening Institutions and Sustainability in Ghana's Cocoa Value Chain*.

World Cocoa Foundation. (2020). *Cocoa & Forests Initiative Annual Report*.

Youth Employment Report. (2022). *Ghana Youth Employment Trends and Priorities*.

Appendices

Abbreviation

Abbreviation Full Meaning

COCOBOD	Ghana Cocoa Board
CRIG	Cocoa Research Institute of Ghana
EPA	Environmental Protection Agency
MoFA	Ministry of Food and Agriculture
GLSS	Ghana Living Standards Survey
CSSVD	Cocoa Swollen Shoot Virus Disease
GDP	Gross Domestic Product
LBC	Licensed Buying Company
FAO	Food and Agriculture Organization
ICCO	International Cocoa Organization
GSS	Ghana Statistical Service
SME	Small and Medium Enterprise
UTZ	UTZ Certified (sustainable farming program)
IITA	International Institute of Tropical Agriculture

Appendix A: Cocoa Producer Prices in Ghana (2018–2024)

Year/Season Producer Price (GHC/tonne) USD Equivalent* Change (%)

Year/Season	Producer Price (GHC/tonne)	USD Equivalent*	Change (%)
2018/19	7,600	~1,350	–
2020/21	10,560	~1,800	+39%
2023/24	33,120 (April 2024)	~2,750	+214%
2024/25	49,600 (Nov. 2024)	~3,750	+50%

*USD equivalent based on mid-year exchange rates (approximate).

Sources: Ghana Cocoa Board (2024); GhanaWeb (2024); Citi Newsroom (2024).

Appendix B: Cocoa Production and Yield Data (2018–2024)

Year	Estimated Production (tonnes)	Average Yield (kg/ha)	Notes
2018	900,000	450–500	Average year
2020	850,000	450	Good rainfall year
2023	~750,000	~420	Disease outbreaks
2024	429,000	<400	Severe impact from CSSVD & smuggling

Source: COCOBOD Annual Reports (2023–2024), Reuters (2024), ICCO.

Appendix C: Common Cocoa Diseases in Ghana

Disease	Cause	Prevalence	Estimated Yield Loss
CSSVD	Virus via mealybugs	High in Eastern & Western North	25–50% (can be total farm loss)
Black Pod	Phytophthora spp.	Rainy season outbreaks	20–30% if uncontrolled
Root Rot	Soil fungi	Waterlogged soils	Moderate

Source: CRIG (2023); EPA Ghana (2022)

Appendix D: Key Stakeholder Roles in Ghana’s Cocoa Sector

Stakeholder	Role
COCOBOD	Sets producer prices, manages inputs, mass spraying, research funding
CRIG	Conducts cocoa breeding, agronomic and disease research
Licensed Buying Companies (LBCs)	Buy cocoa from farmers and pay through COCOBOD
Farmer Cooperatives (e.g., Kuapa Kokoo)	Mobilize farmers for training, Fairtrade access
NGOs (e.g., Solidaridad, Rainforest Alliance)	Promote sustainable farming and certification
Private Processors (e.g., Niche Cocoa, Barry Callebaut)	Invest in value addition and local processing

Appendix E: Case Study – Western North Region

District: Bia West

Farms Surveyed: 30 smallholder cocoa farms

Findings:

- 60% of farmers had trees >30 years old
- Only 35% applied fertilizer in the last season
- 80% affected by CSSVD; 40% had lost at least 1 acre
- Less than 20% had access to an extension officer in 2023
- 55% reported they would discourage their children from continuing cocoa farming

Source: Field data from SEND Ghana (2023); Interviews with Cocoa Platform Ghana

Appendix F: Youth and Employment Insights

Indicator	Data
Average farmer age	51 years
Youth participation in cocoa (ages 18–35)	<10%
Youth preference for non-agriculture jobs	65%
Willingness to farm if cocoa was profitable	72%
Access to land for young farmers	Only 18% reported full access

Source: Barrientos et al. (2007); GSS (2019); World Bank Youth Employment Report (2022)

Annex 1: Government Policy Measures Supporting Sustainability

Policy/Program	Description
Planting for Export and Rural Development (PERD)	Rehabilitating diseased and old cocoa farms, especially for CSSVD
Cocoa Rehabilitation Programme (2020–2025)	GHC 3.2 billion allocated; targeted 156,000 ha affected by CSSVD
LID (Living Income Differential)	\$400/tonne premium aimed at improving farmer incomes (since 2020)
Cocoa Management System (CMS)	Digitizing farmer records, traceability, e-payments
1D1F Cocoa Processing Projects	Over 11 chocolate factories licensed under the industrialization plan

Source: Ghana Cocoa Board (2023), MoFA (2023), World Bank (2022)